

The B2-InF Story

"What inspired B2-InF is a beautiful story of self-reflection" - says Dr. Francisco Güell, Coordinator of the project. It all began over 10 years ago, when a family friend asked him for recommendations regarding assisted reproduction technologies, trusting on his wide expertise in the realm of embryo-development. But unfortunately, the question took him off-guard. Dr. Güell realized that he did not know what to tell her and this quickly became a frustration for him. He simply could not believe that despite years of professional career in the field he could not help a friend out with practical guidelines. It was in this moment that he decided to do anything in his power to change this. He then began his journey of research and analysis, which led him to explore all sides of ART processes, including the psychological impact these have on patients and all the legal factors. *"Early embryo development has been my object of study for more than ten years and, with the rise of assisted human reproduction techniques, I became interested in how these techniques may be affecting the development of the unborn child and the health of those who are born"* - Güell indicates.

Prof. Güell quickly realized that Infertility awareness was lacking among the general public. It was absurd that most people did not know that 10% of our society is now born thanks to the aid of infertility treatments. Things had to change.

It is Francisco Güell's determination to make this happen that brought together key organizations in the field of ART to work together in this pioneering project. *But what is the goal?* The goal of B2-InF is to close the gap between the expectations and needs of society in regard to fertility, and the information about treatments available. It is therefore about empowering society to make better decisions regarding their own reproductive health, starting from a strong base of information and practical standardized guidelines. *"More than a stand-alone project, its preparation has been necessary to fulfill what I am called to do: **Serve the entire community involved in assisted human reproduction, including professionals, patients, governments, and above all, the born from it,**"* - he notes and B2-InF exists to turn this vision into reality.

"The European Commission gave the proposal a 100 out of 100 score, something truly unusual for highly competitive international grant calls," - Francisco Güell highlights. He specifies that the idea for the project has been in the works since 2013 when he presented a study that was ultimately published, after going through eight reviewers, in 2017. Over the years he has

introduced in the academic community *"the need for a view that relates to the exercise of techniques from the axis of responsibility, both including clinics' patients (parental responsibility), as well as professionals and society"*.

The ICS researcher highlights that B2-Inf includes a consortium of 10 partners, who make up "a first-rate team." He details that, although they have diverse backgrounds, their global view will allow him to orient each one's effort and direct them towards fulfilling the project's objectives.

